

Case Studies in Bioeconomy education, training and skills development

Case study sample: Tallinn Creative
Incubator

Estonia

CIVITTA

Tallinn Creative Incubator

1 Abstract

Tallinn Creative Incubator is one of the leading creative business incubators in the Baltic Sea region. Its programmes help accelerate the growth of young enterprises. The incubation programme consists of three stages: the Pre-Incubation Programme, the Incubation Programme, and the Growth Programme. Alumni of these programmes include entrepreneurs in eco-design, mycelium-based materials, and design companies.

2 Target Groups

Entrepreneurs-to-be in the Pre-Incubation program; Entrepreneurs with first customers and prototype ready for the Incubation Program (start-ups, companies in the field of creative and circular-economy); entrepreneurs with product and turnover looking for growth opportunities for the Growth Program.

3 Case Study Category

Entrepreneurial Education

4 Training Provider

Tallinn Creative Incubator

5 Region

Tallinn, Estonia

6 Language

Estonian, English (selected programs only)

7 Objectives of the education Format

N/A

8 Final objective of the education format

1. The incubation programme helps the entrepreneur to create a viable and sustainable small business that enriches the business landscape.
2. The pre-incubation of the Creative Incubator is intended for those who are still thinking about starting their own business.
3. The growth programme helps entrepreneurs find growth opportunities and be sustainable. The programme helps to design a company with a structure that allows specialization and hiring more employees.

9 Scope and context of the education format

1. Pre-Incubation Programme (2 months): Covers topics such as business model and value proposition, product/service life cycle and circular economy, fundamentals of brand strategy and marketing, marketing channels, product/service pricing, and finances.
2. Incubation Programme (9 months): In addition to the topics covered in the pre-incubation programme, it also covers pitching and company presentation. It consists of training sessions, seminars, and networking events (more than 30 thematic events during the programme). Each company receives a personal consultant (up to 2 consultations per month) who guides them through the programme and provides an external perspective. As needed, companies are paired with mentors who offer expertise and advice in specific areas (a total of 8 hours of mentoring during the programme). The programme fosters a community among entrepreneurs participating in it.
3. Growth Programme (6 months): Comprises training sessions, seminars, and networking events; up to 2 consultations per month; and 9 hours of mentoring throughout the programme.

10 Specific Skills and competencies addressed

Entrepreneurial skills, business skills, creative skills, financial skills.

11 European Qualification Framework level/s

N/A

12 Main benefit of the participant

1. With the help of the incubation programme, participants may create a successful and sustainable company and reach your set goals.
2. The pre-incubation participant gets access to a 7-part training program that focuses on the following topics:
 - Business model and value proposition
 - Product / service life cycle and circular economy
 - Fundamentals of brand strategy and marketing
 - Marketing channels
 - Product/service pricing and finances
3. The growth programme of the Creative Incubator helps entrepreneurs find growth opportunities and be sustainable. The program helps to design a company with a structure that allows for specialization and hiring more employees.

13 Investment made

- Pre-Incubation program: Price 60€/month +VAT
- Incubation program: Price 120€ +VAT
- Growth program: Price 90€/month +VAT

14 Importance and impact

The Tallinn Creative Incubator directs companies to incorporate the principles of the circular economy in their business. The need to adapt business models stems from

established regulations and the need to stay competitive. In a situation where small businesses compete with large companies, they gain a competitive advantage in environmentally conscious behavior due to their flexibility and ability to change faster.

The goal of the Creative Incubator is to support sustainable, green and circular economy entrepreneurship through awareness raising and practical solutions.

15 Relevance (of the format)

Tallinn Creative Incubator offers entrepreneurs a tailor-made 24-month development program including a personal business consultant and business mentors who contribute to the success of each business and support their journey on becoming more sustainable. In addition, there are over 50 workshops in a year and joint study visits to fairs and conferences taking place during the incubation programme.

Tallinn Creative Incubator has a wide network of foreign partners to help the companies to international markets.

16 Uniqueness and replicability in BioGov.net

Tallinn Creative Incubator is one of the leading creative business incubators in the Baltic Sea region, it has an excellent 10-year track-record in helping over 300 companies to launch and grow. Many of its incubated companies have attracted large-scale investments and successfully entered international markets. Its innovative and business-centred approach and successful track-record can serve as an important source of inspiration for BioGov.net.

17 Data sources

- **Online resources:** <https://inkubaator.tallinn.ee/en/>
- **Resource persons:**
- **Other sources, if any:**

Consortium

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